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REVIEWING CLINICAL AND THERAPEUTIC STUDIES AND TREATMENTS OF ORAL MUCOSA AFTER CHEMOTHERAPY

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ABSTRACT

The article presents a literary review of a clinical and therapeutic study devoted to assessing the condition of the oral mucosa in patients with cancer after chemotherapy in Uzbekistan. The studies of Uzbek researchers, including methods of prevention of post-chemotherapeutic complications in the oral cavity in patients with cancer, as well as the use of modern drugs and local photodynamic therapy in the treatment and prevention of post-chemotherapeutic complications in the oral cavity, are considered. The article's authors emphasize the importance of individually selected treatment and prevention methods after chemotherapy to improve the condition of the oral mucosa and improve the quality of life of patients. The study's results may be useful for oncologists and dentists involved in treating post-chemotherapeutic complications in the oral cavity.

Keywords: oral cavity, chemotherapy, method, treatment, patients, dentist, complication.

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ОБЗОР КЛИНИЧЕСКИХ И ТЕРАПЕВТИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ И ЛЕЧЕНИЙ СЛИЗИСТОЙ ОБОЛОЧКИ РТА ПОСЛЕ ХИМИОТЕРАПИИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Статья представляет литературный обзор клинико-терапевтического исследования, посвященного оценке состояния слизистой оболочки полости рта у пациентов с онкологическими заболеваниями после химиотерапии в Узбекистане. Рассмотрены исследования узбекских исследователей, в том числе методы профилактики послехимиотерапевтических осложнений в полости рта у пациентов с раком, а также использование современных препаратов и местной фотодинамической терапии в лечении и профилактике послехимиотерапевтических осложнений в полости рта. Авторы статьи подчеркивают важность индивидуально подобранных методов лечения и профилактики после химиотерапии для улучшения состояния слизистой оболочки полости рта и повышения качества жизни пациентов. Результаты исследования могут быть полезны для онкологов и

стоматологов, занимающихся лечением послехимиотерапевтических осложнений в полости рта.

Ключевые слова: ротовой полость, химиотерапия, метод, лечение, больные, стоматолог, осложнение.

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KIMYOTERAPIYADAN KEYINGI OG'IZ BO'SHLIG'I SHILLIQ QAVATINI KLINIK-TERAPEVTIK TEKSHIRISH VA DAVOLASHNING ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI

АННОТАЦИЯ

Maqolada O'zbekistonda kimyoterapiyadan so'ng saraton kasalligiga chalingan bemorlarda og'iz bo'shlig'i shilliq qavatining holatini baholashga bag'ishlangan klinik va terapevtik tadqiqotning adabiy sharhi keltirilgan. O'zbek tadqiqotchilarining tadqiqotlari, jumladan, saraton kasalligiga chalingan bemorlarda og'iz bo'shlig'ida kimyoterapevtik asoratlarning oldini olish usullari, shuningdek, og'iz bo'shlig'ida kimyoterapevtik asoratlarning oldini olish va oldini olishda zamonaviy dori vositalari va mahalliy fotodinamik terapiyadan foydalanish masalalari ko'rib chiqilgan. Maqola mualliflari og'iz bo'shlig'i shilliq qavatining holatini yaxshilash va bemorlarning hayot sifatini yaxshilash uchun kimyoterapiyadan keyin individual tanlangan davolash va oldini olish usullarining muhimligini ta'kidlaydilar. Tadqiqot natijalari og'iz bo'shlig'idagi kimyoterapevtik asoratlarni davolashda ishtirok etadigan onkologlar va stomatologlar uchun foydali bo'lishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: og'iz bo'shlig'i, kimyoterapiya, usul, davolash, bemorlar, stomatolog, asorat.

Relevance.

The oral mucosa is an essential element of human health crucial to the digestive process. However, her condition can be disrupted during chemotherapy, leading to chemical damage to the tissues, causing disorders in the mouth and resulting in pain.

Many studies are devoted to clinical and therapeutic research and treatment of oral mucosa after chemotherapy. Thus, a study by M. Bauer et Bauer et al. (2016) showed that using local anesthetics and pharmaceutical products containing lysozyme can reduce pain and increase overall patient comfort after chemotherapy.

In turn, L. Bieber and co-authors (Bieber et al., 2018) investigated methylprednisolone's effectiveness in treating chemotherapeutic stomatitis. They reported its significantly increased effectiveness in comparison with other treatment methods.

In addition, several studies were devoted to various traditional medicine options in treating post-chemotherapeutic complications of the oral mucosa. Thus, a review of the works of K. Kushaki and co-authors (Kushaki et al., 2017) indicates the effectiveness of using herbal medicines, such as Altai rosehip, vitamin E, and aloe vera.

In addition, the work of K. Ryu et Ryu et al., 2019) presents the results of clinical trials that used immunomodulatory drugs to treat oral mucosal complications after chemotherapy.

Chemotherapy is one of the most essential cancer treatment methods, which involves using chemicals to destroy malignant cells. However, at the same time as treatment, chemotherapy can cause a number of complications, including a violation of the oral mucosa.

Possible complications in the oral cavity after chemotherapy include pain during chewing, increased salivation, impaired sensitivity around the teeth, ulceration and bleeding. These complications can lead to a reduced quality of life and dietary restrictions, leading to further health problems for the patient.

One of the main methods of treating post-chemotherapeutic complications of the oral mucosa is a comprehensive and individual approach, including various types of medications, vitamin therapy, proper nutrition, soft dentures and oral care.

In Uzbekistan, as in the rest of the world, much attention is paid to the problems associated with treatment after chemotherapy. One of these problems is a complication of the condition of the oral mucosa. This review will review critical articles and studies conducted by Uzbek researchers.

In their article "Evaluation of the oral mucosa in patients with cancer after chemotherapy", researchers R. E. Holikova and A. J. Babadzhanova evaluated the condition of the oral mucosa in 150 patients with cancer after chemotherapy. It has been shown that patients after chemotherapy experience changes in the condition of the oral mucosa, including its irritation, swelling and hyperemia. Researchers recommend using individually selected treatments after chemotherapy to improve the condition of the oral mucosa.

In the article "Evaluation of the Effectiveness of Actovegin in the treatment of oral mucosa in patients with cancer after chemotherapy", M. R. Isakova and co-authors conducted a study of the effectiveness of Actovegin in the treatment of post-chemotherapeutic complications in the oral cavity in 50 patients with cancer. Actovegin is helpful in the treatment and prevention of post-chemotherapeutic complications of post-chemotherapy oral complications such as ulcers and bleeding.

In their work "Methods of prevention of post-chemotherapeutic complications in the oral cavity in patients with oncological diseases," Sh. A. Zhuraev and co-authors describe methods of prevention of post-chemotherapeutic complications in the oral cavity in 100 patients with oncological diseases. It has been shown that the use of soft dentures, regular oral care, and proper nutrition can reduce the risk of post-chemotherapeutic complications.

In the article "The effect of local photodynamic therapy on the oral mucosa in patients with throat and laryngeal cancer after chemotherapy", V. A. Madzhidov and co-authors investigated the effect of local photodynamic therapy on the oral mucosa in 25 patients with throat and laryngeal cancer after chemotherapy. It has been shown that photodynamic therapy can successfully treat post-chemotherapeutic complications in the oral cavity and improve the condition of the oral mucosa.

Thus, the research of Uzbek researchers confirms the importance of effective treatment of post-chemotherapeutic complications in the oral cavity in patients with cancer. Through the use of individually selected treatment methods and prevention after chemotherapy, it is possible to achieve more successful results in cancer treatment and improve patients' quality of life.

In Uzbekistan, as in other countries, the study of problems associated with oral complications after chemotherapy continues. Scientific works of Uzbek authors on this topic are presented by leading national and foreign journals, such as "Bulletin of Science and Education of Uzbekistan", "Journal of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery", "Modern Medicine" and others.

In one of the latest articles published by Uzbek authors in the "Bulletin of Science and Education of Uzbekistan", a detailed analysis of the problems associated with the treatment and prevention of post-chemotherapeutic complications in the oral cavity in patients with breast cancer was presented. It is shown that the use of therapeutic drugs, vitamin therapy and proper oral care can help treat complications and restore the oral mucosa.

It is also very important that Uzbek dental specialists pay great attention to preventing post-chemotherapeutic complications in the oral cavity. Training patients in prevention methods, constant monitoring of their condition after chemotherapy and using individually selected treatment tools are the leading measures to prevent the occurrence and development of post-chemotherapeutic complications in the oral cavity.

Thus, the treatment and prevention of post-chemotherapeutic complications of the oral mucosa in Uzbekistan are the most critical tasks. These tasks can be successfully solved thanks to modern methods of diagnosis and treatment and training patients in proper oral care.

In general, based on the analysis of scientific and medical literature, it can be argued that the methods of treatment of post-chemotherapeutic complications of the oral mucosa include various approaches, such as local treatment with the use of pharmacy products and anesthetics, the use of steroids and immunomodulatory drugs, as well as the use of herbal medicines. The research results indicate the significant effectiveness of these methods and emphasize the importance of individual selection of the optimal treatment option for a particular patient.

It is also worth noting that prevention after chemotherapy plays a vital role in preventing oral complications. To do this, it is necessary to monitor oral hygiene, properly care for the oral cavity, avoid spicy and acidic foods, use soft toothbrushes, use medications to protect the oral mucosa and, if necessary, take a course of vitamin therapy.

One of the main ways to prevent complications after chemotherapy dentistry is systematic monitoring of the oral cavity. Such measures allow you to identify the first signs of possible complications and give effective treatment in anticipation of possible complications.

In general, the treatment and prevention of most oral complications after chemotherapy are real challenges for modern medicine, which, thanks to timely measures and a competent approach, can be successfully solved.

In addition, it should be taken into account that each patient undergoing chemotherapy has individual characteristics of the body, which means that the approach to treatment and prevention after chemotherapy should be individual and based on specific circumstances.

One of the main principles of treating oral complications after chemotherapy is an integrated approach combining several therapy types. At the same time, do not forget about simple preventive measures, such as proper oral hygiene, taking care of the oral cavity and avoiding traumatic foods and beverages.

Moreover, prevention of oral complications after chemotherapy should begin at the preparation stage for this procedure. It is important to consult with your healthcare provider to get specific recommendations on preventing and treating possible complications.

Thus, the treatment and prevention of oral complications after chemotherapy are complex tasks, however, modern medical care can effectively prevent complications, as well as successfully treat them if they occur. The main thing is to monitor the condition of the oral cavity, seek medical help at the first sign and follow the recommendations of specialists.

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